

Teachers' Views on Leadership and Management in Higher Education EFL Contexts: A Qualitative Investigation in Türkiye

Cemile BUĞRA¹ 0000-0002-3441-7109

Sezer Alper ZEREYALP² 0000-0002-1217-3430

<p>ARTICLE HISTORY</p> <p>Received 10 Mar 2026 Accepted 6 May 2026</p> <p>KEYWORDS</p> <p>higher education; EFL context; teacher views; teacher leadership; teacher empowerment; leadership and management skills</p>	<p>ABSTRACT</p> <p>Leadership and management have long been recognized as pivotal constructs within educational research. Despite the substantial body of research highlighting their prominence in educational contexts, relatively few qualitative studies have explored EFL teachers' perspectives on leadership and management in higher education settings. The present study is important since it addresses a significant gap in existing research by focusing on the issue from the perspectives of EFL teachers. The participants of this study are EFL instructors (12 females and 3 males) who work in the school of foreign languages in different university contexts in Türkiye. The data were gathered through an open-ended survey and a focus group discussion. The findings of the study reveal that all the participant EFL teachers have diverse perspectives about leadership and management depending on their contexts, qualifications, backgrounds, experiences, and the administrative guidance that they received. Even the teachers who work in the same contexts have different views and perceptions about the issue. It also shows that most of the participating EFL instructors are aware of the importance of teacher leadership, management and empowerment, even though some of them limit the dimensions of these concepts to their classroom only, rather than approaching it from a broadened perspective.</p>
---	---

Introduction

The trends and needs are increasingly changing and expanding in the educational contexts so fast, and teachers are expected to adapt to those changes in their profession as fast as possible. (Ash & Persall, 2000). However, the development of these trends and processes tends to be time-consuming, as they are affected by a number of factors such as teachers' working conditions, professional roles and responsibilities, and willingness to participate. In recent years, teacher leadership and teacher empowerment have therefore become central topics closely associated with the teaching profession. The 19th-century factory model of schools, in which decisions are made in a rigid and top-down fashion, identifies principals as managers, teachers as workers and students as raw material has changed (Hynes et al., 1992). Accordingly, the concept of teacher leadership and its importance for the improvement of the schools have been publicly recognised since the beginning of the 20th century (Smylie et al., 2002).

The importance of leadership has been highlighted in the literature since it leads to generating and sustaining school improvement and change (Childs-Bowen et al., 2000; Day & Harris, 2003). In order to provide students with quality education to be successful in society and to deal with complex changes, schools are required to adopt new approaches (Harris, 2002) and teachers must expand their own capabilities, and undertake greater leadership roles (Ash & Persall, 2000) because effective leadership can boost overall school performance, improve instructional quality, and motivate teachers to realize their full potential (Andrianto et al., 2023). Importantly, teacher leadership also has reciprocal effects on teachers themselves. Katzenmeyer and Moller (2001) report that teacher leaders experience professional growth, shifting collegial relationships, and enhanced leadership capacity, though sometimes

¹ Dr., Çukurova University, School of Foreign Languages, cmlbgr@gmail.com.

² Dr., Çukurova University, School of Foreign Languages, alperzereyalp@gmail.com.

accompanied by increased stress and role ambiguity. These findings indicate that teacher leadership consists of identity negotiation and boundary crossing between peer and leadership roles.

Recent academic studies mark the potential of teacher leadership as a key component in discussions surrounding educational reform and change. A growing body of contemporary literature argues that teachers should assume a more influential role in decision-making processes and policy development within education systems. Within this perspective, the concept of “flipping the system” has gained prominence, suggesting a transformation toward positioning teachers as the primary drivers, designers, and implementers of educational change (Netolicky et al., 2018; Rycroft-Smith & Dutaut, 2018).

Despite the growing body of research on educational leadership and teacher leadership, relatively limited attention has been paid to how EFL instructors in higher education perceive and interpret leadership and administrative practices within their institutional contexts. This is especially important as tensions may arise when managerial expectations, accountability mechanisms, and performance-oriented policies intersect with academic traditions that emphasise collaboration and professional autonomy (Deem et al., 2007). The present study aims to address this gap by exploring how EFL teachers in higher education define and experience leadership and management, the leadership roles they fulfil, their perceptions of teacher empowerment, and the ways in which they are allowed to develop leadership capacities within their professional contexts.

Research Questions

The current study aims to address the following research questions:

1. How do EFL teachers define and perceive the concepts of leadership and management in higher education contexts?
2. What kind of leadership roles do EFL teachers have in higher education contexts, and how do they perceive these roles?
3. What kind of experiences do EFL teachers have regarding teacher empowerment in higher education contexts?

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

Educational leadership has been examined through several theoretical perspectives that explain how leadership practices have an impact on organisational functioning and educational outcomes. Early approaches were largely based on managerial and bureaucratic models emphasising planning, coordination, and organisational efficiency (Bush, 2011). Following theoretical developments shifted attention toward leadership as a process of influence and change. Contemporary leadership theories have significantly reshaped and reframed how educational leadership is perceived. One of the most influential perspectives is transformational leadership, with the emphasis on the role of leaders in aligning followers towards a shared vision, motivating members of the organisation, and fostering professional commitment and collective capacity for change (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2000). Within this framework, leadership is not limited to formal authority and involves inspiring followers and developing their potential to achieve shared goals. In contrast, instructional leadership predominantly focuses on improving teaching and learning processes by prioritising curriculum coordination, instructional quality, and student achievement (Hallinger, 2003).

Another perspective that has gained attention in leadership literature is servant leadership, which emphasises service, collaboration, and the development of others within the organisation. Originally conceptualised by Greenleaf (1977), this approach positions the

leader not at the top of a hierarchical structure but as an individual who works closely with organisational members and prioritises their professional and personal needs (Northouse, 2019). In this sense, leadership is interpreted as a relational process that seeks to empower followers and cultivate a supportive organisational climate. Similarly, situational leadership theory suggests that effective leadership depends on the leader's ability to adapt leadership behaviours according to the competence, motivation, and needs of followers (Hersey, Blanchard, & Johnson, 2013). Rather than relying on a single leadership style, this approach underlines the importance of flexibility and responsiveness to contextual conditions, allowing leadership roles to shift depending on the demands of particular situations.

More recent perspectives challenge leader-centred models and emphasise collaborative forms of leadership. Distributed leadership theory, for example, conceptualises leadership as a practice emerging through interactions among multiple actors within an organisation rather than being confined to formal leadership positions (Spillane, 2006; Harris, 2008). In a similar vein, teacher leadership perspectives highlight teachers' roles as agents of change who contribute to professional learning, decision-making, and school improvement beyond their individual classrooms (York-Barr & Duke, 2004). All these theoretical perspectives indicate a shift in educational leadership from traditional hierarchical models toward more collaborative, relational, and practice-oriented frameworks that recognise the contributions of multiple actors within educational organisations.

Teacher Leadership

Although teacher leadership has attracted increasing attention over the past three decades, the concept remains conceptually and theoretically fragmented. It has been noted that there is still no clear consensus regarding how teacher leadership should be defined or framed (Neumerski, 2012). Similarly, Harris (2003) points out that the term is often characterised by overlapping interpretations and definitional ambiguity within the literature. This ambiguity may result from the diverse roles associated with teacher leadership, including responsibilities such as mentoring, coordinating, leading departments, coaching colleagues, and supporting curriculum development (Mangin & Stoelinga, 2008). These varied titles reflect various institutional arrangements, making teacher leadership a context-dependent phenomenon rather than a standardised role. Hence, conceptualisations of teacher leadership are widely varied. For instance, Wasley (1991) defines teacher leadership as the ability to lead colleagues for change and to do things they would not usually consider without the support of the leader. On the other hand, York-Barr and Duke (2004) claim that 'teacher leadership is the process by which teachers, individually or collectively, influence their colleagues, principals, and other members of school communities to improve teaching and learning practices with the aim of increased student learning and achievement'. Similarly, Katzenmeyer and Moller (2009) define teacher leaders as teachers who not only lead within the classroom but also beyond the classroom through contributing to a community of teacher learners and leaders, influencing others towards improved educational practice, and accepting responsibility for achieving outcomes. Teacher leadership refers to practices that go beyond teachers' formally defined responsibilities, including activities such as sharing professional knowledge and initiating change within the school (Baker-Doyle, 2017). Transforming schools into professional learning communities, which are basically associated with improved instruction and increased student achievement, is also expected as an outcome of teacher leadership (Smylie & Wenzel, 2003). Teacher leadership also includes influencing fellow teachers, students, and other school stakeholders either individually or collectively in the direction of common goals regarding teaching and learning improvements (Hairon et al., 2015). As teacher leaders influence other colleagues to improve their teaching practices, they are also perceived as the change agents (Cooper et al., 2016). Similarly, in teacher leadership, there is a redistribution of power in schools that shifts from hierarchical control to peer control (Nafia & Suyatno, 2020). All these

various definitions and descriptions focusing on different aspects highlight the necessity of addressing teacher leadership through its various dimensions.

Frost and Durrant (2003) outline teacher leadership on normative grounds through four main arguments: enhancing school effectiveness, supporting school improvement, strengthening teacher morale and retention, and fostering democratic principles. These arguments portray teacher leadership as both instrumentally beneficial, in terms of improving educational outcomes, and normatively important, as it can encourage participation and empowerment. Nevertheless, these claims are frequently based on the assumption that institutional cultures are convenient for sharing power. Wenner and Campbell's (2017) study demonstrated that school norms and organisational structures can either empower or marginalise teacher leaders. Thus, teacher leadership is not just an individual capability but a structurally mediated practice.

Leadership and Management in Educational Contexts

More recent perspectives challenge leader-centred models and emphasise collaborative forms of leadership, which underlines the importance of interactions among teachers, administrators, and other stakeholders in shaping educational improvement and organisational learning. In particular, distributed leadership conceptualises leadership as a practice emerging through interactions among multiple actors within an organisation rather than being limited to formal positions (Spillane, 2006; Harris, 2008). Similarly, teacher leadership perspectives highlight teachers' roles as agents of change who contribute to professional learning, decision-making, and school improvement outside their classrooms as well (York-Barr & Duke, 2004). Taken together, these theoretical perspectives indicate a shift in educational leadership from traditional hierarchical models to more collaborative and practice-oriented frameworks.

Traditional models of school systems were largely influenced by bureaucratic and hierarchical assumptions. What is often referred to as the "factory model" positions principals as managers, teachers as practitioners, and students as outputs of a production system (Hynes et al., 1992). This framework can be said to prioritise management efficiency over professional agency. However, with the growing complexity of educational contexts affected by globalisation, pedagogical innovation, and accountability-driven policies, leadership has increasingly been understood as a transformative process rather than merely an administrative function." (Day & Harris, 2003). The distinction between leadership and management has long been debated in organisational theory and educational administration. While management is typically associated with planning, organising, coordinating, and maintaining institutional stability, leadership is concerned with vision-building, influence, and change (Bush, 2011; Northouse, 2019). This distinction has recently become particularly significant in educational settings because schools and universities are not solely bureaucratic structures but complex social organisations led by professional expectations and pedagogical needs.

Leadership and Management in Higher Education

Leadership and management roles in higher education involve a complex combination of managerial responsibilities and academic leadership functions. Universities are often characterised as professional bureaucracies in which academic staff have considerable autonomy while administrative leaders manage institutional processes and support teaching and research activities (Bush, 2011). Within this organisational structure, administrators such as department chairs, program coordinators, and directors of academic units undertake multiple responsibilities including policy implementation, resource allocation, curriculum coordination, and faculty support (Gmelch & Buller, 2015). These roles require balancing managerial duties with academic leadership practices aimed at enhancing instructional

quality and fostering professional collaboration among faculty members. In many cases, mid-level administrators act as intermediaries between institutional leadership and academic staff, communicating institutional goals and policies into everyday practices within educational programs (Bryman, 2007).

Leadership and Management in Foreign Language Education

Leadership practices in language education programs share many characteristics with the broader leadership context in higher education, but also involve context-dependent responsibilities related to language teaching and curriculum programming. In university language preparatory programs and EFL departments, administrators, program directors, or coordinators are often responsible for organising curriculum development, establishing assessment systems, supporting teacher professional development, and enabling communication among instructors and institutional leadership (Bailey, 2006). These roles require balancing managerial duties with pedagogical leadership to improve language instruction and support teacher development. At the same time, language program leadership typically operates in academic settings where instructors value professional autonomy and disciplinary expertise (Knight, 2001). As a result, program administrators are frequently expected to act as mediators who negotiate between institutional policies, quality assurance processes, and instructors' professional responsibilities. Effective leadership in language programs often depends on collaborative and participative decision-making and supportive professional cultures that encourage shared responsibility for the improvement of the programs (Bailey, 2006). Thus, examining instructors' perceptions of leadership and administrative practices in EFL contexts can provide key insights into how leadership is experienced and enacted within language education settings.

Methodology

The present study adopted a qualitative research design to explore EFL instructors' perceptions of leadership and management in higher education contexts. A qualitative approach was considered to be particularly appropriate to capture participants' perspectives and provide an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon (Creswell, 2013). In line with this, Burn (1997) asserts that the purpose of the qualitative researcher is to conceptualise what people say and do as a product of how they perceive the world and interpret the events from the perspectives of the participants. Accordingly, this study adopted a qualitative research design in order to gain an in-depth understanding of teachers' beliefs, views, and practices on teacher leadership, as reflected in their own words and experiences. With these in mind, the data were gathered through an open-ended survey and a focus group discussion.

Sampling

The current study applied purposive sampling to determine its participants. Purposive sampling was used in order to select the participants from whom the most relevant and reliable information could be gathered (Patton, 2002). To apply this sampling, the criterion was that all the teachers were EFL teachers who had different educational backgrounds, various years of teaching experience, and were working in different Turkish university contexts. Additionally, it was aimed to explore the experiences of educators who work in a variety of educational settings. Therefore, several English language instructors employed by state universities were contacted in order to reach the target audience as effectively as possible. Prior to the data collection process, the participants were informed about the purpose of the study and their consent was obtained for the use of the data for academic purposes. They were informed that their names would be kept anonymous. To this end, the participants were EFL teachers who worked at six different university contexts in Türkiye.

Participants

This exploratory study was conducted with fifteen volunteer EFL teachers (13 female, 2 male) from six different state university contexts in Türkiye. Thirteen of them were Turkish, while two of them were from different nationalities, namely Polish and Ukrainian. They all had different backgrounds. During the data collection process, four participants had PhD degrees, and the other four teachers were PhD candidates. Five participants had an MA degree. However, only two of the teachers had a BA degree. Whereas six of them had some kind of administrative role, nine of them did not have any roles like this during their professional lives. Two of these teachers had less than ten years of experience, and seven of them had more than ten years of experience. However, six of them had more than twenty years of experience. Finally, ten participants were working in the same context, while the five others were working in five different university contexts. Detailed information is shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1

Demographic Information

Teachers	Origin	Gender	Degree	Years of Experience	Administrative Role
T1	Turkish	Male	MA	27	No
T2	Turkish	Female	PhD	20	No
T3	Turkish	Female	PhD Candidate	8	Yes (Board Member)
T4	Polish	Female	PhD Candidate	2	No
T5	Turkish	Female	MA	29	Yes (Unit Coordinator)
T6	Turkish	Female	PhD Candidate	25	No
T7	Turkish	Female	PhD	10	Yes (Unit Coordinator)
T8	Ukrainian	Female	MA	10	Yes (Unit Coordinator)
T9	Turkish	Female	BA	29	No
T10	Turkish	Female	PhD	12	No
T11	Turkish	Male	PhD Candidate	17	Yes (Assistant Director)
T12	Turkish	Female	BA	25	No
T13	Turkish	Female	MA	13	No
T14	Turkish	Female	MA	10	Yes (Unit Coordinator)
T15	Turkish	Male	PhD	12	No

Data Collection Instruments and Procedure

Open-Ended Survey

First, primary data were collected through a survey consisting of open-ended questions to allow participants to express their views in detail. The survey involves 9 open-ended questions, and they were prepared by the first researcher. It was revised based on the comments and expert opinions before it was given to all the participants. Open-ended survey questions were used to identify teachers' self-reported views, beliefs, experiences and practices about leadership and management issues in EFL contexts. Demographic information was included in the survey, which gives details about the nature of the study and asks for the consent of the

participants in the following. The survey was shared as a hard copy with some of the participants, while some of the participants preferred to answer via email.

Focus Group Discussion

A focus group discussion was administered by the researchers with the participation of five EFL teachers (T2, T3, T6, T8, T11) to ensure data triangulation. Data obtained from open-ended surveys were followed by a focus group discussion to create an environment where participants could express their perspectives transparently and elaborate on their opinions in a comprehensive manner. Emerging themes from the primary findings were reevaluated and discussed by the volunteer participants during the focus group discussion with the guidance of the researchers. They reevaluated the emerging themes and tried to reflect on them one more time with a broadened perspective to strengthen the data and make sure that various perspectives were involved.

Data Analysis

Qualitative data were analysed using thematic analysis, drawing on the six steps of the thematic analysis approach as suggested by Braun and Clarke (2006). To ensure the credibility of the findings, member checking was conducted during initial data analysis to clarify ambiguous responses and verify the accuracy of the researchers' interpretations. The researcher asked some follow-up questions to the participants informally when some clarification was needed to verify the data. By the time all these steps were completed, the data were classified based on the aspects investigated in the study. As Creswell (2013) outlines, data analysis entails a preliminary examination of the database, followed by coding, theme organisation, representation, and interpretation (p. 195). In line with this framework, the present study adopted a systematic and iterative approach to analysing the collected data. The first researcher made the initial analysis while collecting the data. Later on, the initial findings were checked and reevaluated by the second researcher. And then, the researchers negotiated on the emerging themes a couple of times. The data analysis was conducted collaboratively until the researchers reached an agreement on the emerging themes. However, they finalised the analysis after a series of meetings.

Results

Teachers' Definitions on Leadership and Management

In the present study, participant teachers were asked to define the concepts of leadership and management in their own words. An analysis of their responses revealed that they approached these concepts from a variety of perspectives. In particular, many participants elaborated more extensively on the concept of leadership. The reason for that may be because they are mostly interested in leadership rather than management. Many respondents describe leadership as the ability to guide, inspire, and motivate others towards a common goal. There is a strong emphasis on responsibility, role modelling, and empowering others. The participant teachers' views on leadership are like these:

T4: Leadership means that teachers can come up with their own ideas and take initiative to solve problems that might occur in their job. It means that teachers can be active reformers rather than passive implementers.

T7: Leaders become role models and are loved by their workers.

T10: Leadership means motivating and supporting a group of people to achieve a common goal together, understanding people and tailoring work/responsibility accordingly.

On the other hand, management is commonly viewed as the process of organising, controlling, and administering tasks, resources, and people within an institution. Respondents describe it

as a more structured and administrative function compared to leadership. The extracts below reveal teachers' ideas clearly:

T1: Management is having the assignment authority and applying it. However, this does not mean that the person appointed has all the skills required for the post. It requires special education and leadership skills.

T8: Management means finding rational and logical solutions for complex problems.

T11: Management is the act of using limited resources in the most effective way. It may be managing people, an institution, or a business.

T15: Management is running "the engine", which happens to be a school/institution in our field. It necessitates a high level of professionalism, leadership and very meticulous prioritisation skills.

The majority of teachers participating in this study conceptualised management predominantly from an administrative standpoint, emphasising extrinsic dimensions rather than approaching it as a personal matter shaped by intrinsic factors. Only a small group of teachers evaluated management in relation to pedagogical concerns and classroom practices. The following excerpts illustrate these perspectives in more detail:

T3: It is about being able to manage many things. There are different kinds of management. We can talk about classroom management and time management.

However, clearly it was difficult for some participants to distinguish between leadership and management, frequently including aspects of one concept within the definition of the other. For example, while defining management, they included leadership skills. Most of the participants made a clear distinction between the two concepts. Several respondents differentiated between leadership and management, highlighting how both are crucial yet distinct. While leadership is often linked to inspiration, vision, and empowering others, management is associated with coordination, execution, and resource optimisation for EFL teachers more. The views of some participants are provided below:

T5: Leadership means coordinating people's activities and using their potential. Management means managing people and problem-solving.

T7: Leadership is about leading the work by cooperating with the workers. Management is related to organising, sourcing, staff, and materials.

T14: Leadership is taking initiative, being flexible, and guiding a team efficiently through challenges. Management is checking and organising staff and work.

Teachers' Views on the Leadership Roles

The results revealed that only six of the participants had administrative roles in their professional lives. Teachers think that their responsibilities, other than teaching, such as coordinating the Testing and Evaluation Office, Erasmus Office, Mevlana Office and International Relations Office, are a part of administration. Three of the participants who have these administrative roles talked about their general responsibilities. However, the others reflect on the issue in detail. There is only one participant who works as the vice director in his own context, and he focuses on communication issues as follows:

T11: I have an ongoing administrative role. I have been the vice director in my context. This position requires a good amount of patience and communication skills.

Similarly, another participant touches upon the same issue, and she says:

T7: I worked as an Erasmus Coordinator at the department of the university, then I became the Foreign Language Education Coordinator at the university. Since the workload and the

responsibility have increased, it makes you feel a bit tense. However, I am very attentive to listening to my colleagues and not to break anyone's heart.

On the other hand, one participant focuses on the advantages of working as a coordinator rather than talking about the challenges of that position, and she expresses this way:

T14: I worked at the International Relations Office for 4 years. At first, it was a bit challenging to learn about the responsibilities because they are very different from those of a regular teacher's duties. Over time, I gained experience and learned how to work with a team effectively, guiding them whenever necessary. I was able to foresee some problematic areas before they happened, which was very beneficial and gained through experience.

As for the other participants, nine of them stated that they had never had an administrative position before. Yet, they reflected on the issue from their point of view based on their personal experiences in their own specific contexts. While some of them talk about general administrative issues such as decision making, assignments, human relations, etc., some others just focus on classroom management issues, professional development and social organisations. Their views on the issue are like these:

T1: To make a change, I wouldn't present the alternatives and ask the employees to make a choice. I would present the issue and ask for their ideas, and have a discussion on these.

T12: I would first ask the team about their opinions and act accordingly. Sharing ideas and applying a mixture to make it work well is the best way.

T13: If I had an administrative role, I would inform the people around me about the incoming duties and responsibilities as early as I can. I would distribute the duties equally. I would get different opinions before making significant decisions.

T15: If I had an administrative role within my context, I'd definitely go for an increased amount of transparency. Since most administrators nowadays skip assigning duties in writing, they cannot be held accountable in the case of mistakes/problems, which is a serious problem. Transparency would increase accountability, making everyone more careful.

T2: I would like to change task sharing. I would choose the people for a task according to their qualifications and adequacy. Because I think people have different weaknesses or strengths.

T6: I would bring some strict rules for students to deserve their places in the class. These rules would stop them from participating in the class activities, and they will also prevent misbehaviour in the classroom. I would also reduce the workload of teachers to spare more time for their professional development.

T4: I think I would offer that teachers have some professional development courses. We could learn new techniques of teaching, classroom management, and the use of technology in the classroom.

T9: I would like to arrange social organisations or seminars which help people get together.

As reflected in the teachers' excerpts, participants tended to emphasise certain issues they considered to be more significant, often mentioning them in relation to their personal experiences and the challenges they encounter in their professional lives and current work environments.

Teachers' Views on Their Own Leadership and Management Skills

Twelve of the participants believe that teachers should have leadership skills for some reasons, such as motivating the students, controlling the class, managing the class, and directing the students. Additionally, some of the teachers reflect more on this as shared below:

T2: They should have leadership skills since they are the maestro (leader) of the class, and they are also part of a teaching team. Because they conduct their own teaching, students' learning, and information exchange with their colleagues and administration. They have to contribute to a change/changes in their teaching environment so as to make an improvement for both themselves and the education context they work in.

T14: I believe they should have leadership skills because teachers always deal with groups of students. Being a teacher does not only mean teaching the lesson to those students. On the contrary, it means being a facilitator, guide, counsellor, leader, and many more things at the same time. It is important to be able to guide students according to their needs, and this sometimes calls for leadership skills.

On the contrary, while one of the participant teachers finds it impossible for all teachers to have leadership skills, two of the participants do not agree with the others on this issue for the following reasons they shared:

T7: I think some teachers are not grown in this way within their family or during their school years.

T15: I think leadership is not a priority for teachers unless they are the policy makers themselves. Essentially, a teacher is expected to apply the teaching policy of an institution/country as is, and adherence to the policy is a more important part of teaching than leading. However, classroom management may require a certain extent of leadership skills, so a total absence of them would not be desirable in the case of teaching.

All things considered, almost all of the participating teachers believe that teachers should have leadership skills, whereas a few of them find it difficult because of the reasons they gave above. They try to comment on the issue objectively, and they evaluate the issue from a critical perspective, but this does not mean that they totally disagree on the issue.

Teachers' Approaches Towards Leadership

EFL teachers approached leadership from four different aspects, such as student-centred leadership, collaborative skills, problem-solving and analytical skills, communication skills and resistance to formal leadership roles.

Student-Centred Leadership

Many teachers see leadership as guiding and motivating students rather than administrative roles, since they do not think that they are expected to have leadership skills. Leadership is expressed through fairness, encouragement, and fostering active participation in the classroom. For these participants, leadership is about teaching and guiding students, not taking on extra responsibilities and preferring instead to focus on leadership within the classroom. Below are some excerpts from instructors' responses:

T1: I try to involve as many of the students as possible to actively take part during the lesson (in fact, all of them!).

T4: I don't think that I have leadership skills. If we are talking about being a leader as a part of being a teacher, since I am a leader in my classroom, I think that caring for the students is important. I care about their progress and that they actually learn something. I encourage them, but I try to make them study as well. As for qualities it requires, I think it is being committed, helpful, encouraging, and strict.

T6: I am not sure if I have good leadership skills, but I am fair and respectful to all my students.

Collaborative Skills

Several responses underline the importance of cooperation with colleagues and the value of collective work. Most of the teachers associate leadership with building collaborative environments and valuing teamwork. Effective teaching and leadership involve working together with colleagues and fostering a team-oriented environment. The quotations below provide a summary of the responses in this regard:

T3: There are lots of opportunities to learn from others in any condition. I believe in the power of cooperation and collaboration. If we work on sth. altogether, the outcomes will be richer and fruitful but while working alone, everything is limited.

T7: I am good at teamwork and act cooperatively. I think they are very important. We observe what terrible consequences there might be when the administrators lack these skills. They like giving orders and making you have hard times.

T12: Leadership is related to joining people together and encouraging them to do the task enthusiastically.

Problem-Solving and Analytical Skills

Participants' views suggest that effective leadership requires the ability to solve problems proactively and make informed decisions that support the learning environment. Some participants emphasise the importance of analytical thinking and problem-solving as leadership skills. Leadership involves anticipating challenges and finding constructive solutions, especially during decision-making processes. Some excerpts are shared below:

T9: I have a good relationship with people, and I like focusing on solutions.

T11: In my case, I suppose my ability to compromise and convince people to help me. When you make a decision, you should apply your decision by persuading your subordinates on the usefulness of that decision. I believe that these are required skills for leaders.

T14: I am a good observer. I try to solve potential problems before they occur. If I encounter a problem or challenge, I try to find the best solution. I focus on how to best solve a problem or overcome an issue instead of stressing myself and others out.

Communication Skills

Effective communication, both verbal and non-verbal, and interpersonal skills are considered to be vital for leadership in education. This refers to the capacity to communicate ideas clearly, practice active listening, and promote the sharing of ideas among subordinates. Some excerpts to support these views are provided below:

T3: I believe that I am good at listening to people and understanding them and helping them in case they have a problem about their personal or professional lives. Even if I do not agree with my friends, I always create space for them to share their personal opinions and experiences.

T5: I think I am good at listening to people, which is important if you want to understand and motivate them.

T10: I try to be understanding and kind, and to motivate people to share ideas.

Resistance to Formal Leadership Roles

Some respondents express reluctance toward formal leadership roles, particularly administrative positions, for some other reasons. Participants' views on this issue are demonstrated by the following excerpts:

T2: I do not think that I have leadership skills because I do not like to convey my thoughts or ideas verbally much. However, I think I am hardworking and determined; I do not easily give up.

I definitely believe that they help me in my profession. I guess I can be a good role model for my students.

T4: I don't want to be a leader (meaning an administrator). In our institution being a leader means doing extra work without getting any benefits from it.

T15: I do not consider myself having leadership skills as I prefer to work alone and independently whenever possible.

Teachers' Views on Key Characteristics of a Successful School Leader/Administrator

Participants were asked to reflect on the key characteristics of a successful school leader/administrator. Five sub-themes emerged as a result of the analysis. These themes are professional competence and experience, interpersonal skills, organisation and managerial skills, problem-solving skills, consistency and accountability.

Professional Competence and Experience

Most of the teachers believe that school administrators should be open to new ideas, innovations, and ongoing professional development. Their comments are presented below:

T1: S/he should have sufficient teaching experience in the related context. S/he should have formal training and administrative skills.

T5: They also need to set a good example so that others would follow them.

T13: They need to follow new trends.

T6: They should be well-informed about innovations about education.

Nevertheless, one participant compares the state universities with the private universities and talks about what makes them successful in the following excerpt:

T8: I observe general static dogmatic ambiance at state universities in Turkey. No way to provide high standards, leadership and professional management. Private universities are more dynamic, trendy and modern institutions. The administration is younger and more skilful in management there.

Interpersonal Skills

A widely shared view among participants was that effective administrators should demonstrate strong interpersonal skills, show respect toward others, and treat all individuals fairly. Effective administrators should possess strong interpersonal skills, be respectful, and treat everyone fairly. The reflections of the respondents are presented below:

T1: S/he should treat others in a respectful manner and speak in a respectable tone of voice. Also, s/he should have good interpersonal skills.

T6: They should be fair, respectful, know how to listen and make fair judgements.

T7: They should be kind, smiling, making good compliments to their teachers and giving appraisals and gifts to their teachers, keeping justice.

T9: A good administrator should interact with the staff well and try to understand him/her. I think empathy is really precious.

T12: Being close to the teachers and students, sharing ideas and informing them are crucial.

T14: They should also be in contact with their teacher teams all the time and should listen to them regarding issues related to education and students.

Organisational and Managerial Skills

EFL teachers propose that effective school administrators must be highly organised, disciplined, and capable of managing multiple tasks and responsibilities. The following excerpts illustrate participants' views:

T2: A successful administrator must be farsighted, intelligent, flexible, well-organized.

T4: A good school principal should be organized and disciplined because usually they have a lot of things to take care of.

T2: They must choose the right people for the tasks to be held. Based on the needs, they must select the person having the required qualifications.

T9: Planning ability, responsibility and ability to make good decisions are important.

T10: They should be motivating, understanding, showing what to do, tracking the process, taking part in the process actively.

T5: They also need to set a good example so that others would follow them.

Problem-Solving Skills

Most of the teachers agree that administrators need to be excellent problem solvers, flexible, and they should be able to make sound decisions in complex situations. The following statements exemplify these views:

T3: They should be open-minded, understanding, critical and good at problem solving. Mostly, they face lots of problems and they need to be patient and tolerant while solving the problems and they need to focus on solutions rather than problems.

T2: A successful administrator must foresee possible problems that may occur beforehand and think/find solutions for them.

T4: They have to have strong work ethics as well since they have to deal with different types of problems.

T14: I mean they should understand the necessities and challenges they come across and act accordingly.

Consistency and Accountability

Consistency in leadership is accepted to be essential for a stable learning environment since it leads to clear communication of rules and expectations. Fairness, justice, and equity are believed to be crucial as they maintain authority and morale, ensuring that all individuals are treated equally and justly. The respondents' views are shared below:

T2: They must behave with every member equally.

T11: The key characteristic for a school leader is being just, tolerant and predictable. All rules and regulations should be equally applied. Everyone needs to know what they are expected to do and what administrative sanctions are to be applied if they fail to fulfil their responsibilities.

T8: To keep the balance in everything and avoid double standards are important.

Furthermore, some teachers suggest that successful administrators must be transparent in their actions and decisions, fostering accountability and trust within the school. Their quotations are as follows:

T15: A successful leader should be transparent before everything else because it is what makes them accountable for what happens in an institution. Without transparency, there is no reason to trust an administrator. And without trust, there is no way to be intrinsically motivated to

improve the teaching/learning context. More transparency and accountability are all we need for effective leaders and managers.

T1: If an administration senses that there is growing dissatisfaction about and opposition to them, it should be involved in the self-evaluation process, or perhaps display the dignity to announce that it is doing sth. wrong. At this stage, it is better for them to leave the post and support those who will embrace all those involved with fresh energy and enthusiasm. "Mental fatigue" is the worst risk in a working apparatus.

Supports of School Management

EFL teachers were asked to share whether they are supported by their administration in terms of leadership and management issues. Four sub-themes emerged

Support for Professional Development

Most of the teachers report that school management supports teachers' professional growth by providing opportunities for further education and participation in academic events. The quotations below exemplify this:

T3: They support teachers if the teachers try to do projects or research.

T11: Our School Management tries to support teachers in their academic work by being flexible in their timetables and allocating some money for their travel expenses.

T14: Our school regularly provides us with teacher training programmes, seminars and workshops. Sometimes, they invite experts in the field to our institution.

T15: Academic work is always encouraged through making it possible to attend conferences, congresses or professional courses.

T6: School management allows teachers to do their MA and PHD degrees and attend conferences provided that teachers have make-up classes after the conference or find a teacher who will act as a substitute.

Recognition and Appreciation

School managements acknowledge and appreciate teachers' efforts, particularly in academic and extracurricular contributions. Teachers feel valued when contributions are recognised, though sometimes this support is conditional. Some EFL instructors reflected on the issue below:

T2: If the teachers make any contribution to education, such as attending conferences, writing articles, doing projects, they appraise them.

T7: As long as I obey the rules and do not act with a bad intention, they stand by me, I guess.

T9: They listen to the problems and try to find solutions.

Emotional and Personal Support

Effective communication and responsiveness to teacher concerns are seen as supportive actions. Beyond academics, some managements provide support in personal and family matters, showing empathy and understanding. Participants' experiences are shared below:

T3: They try to create a friendly atmosphere for sharing and contributing to the development of the school and the program.

T5: The management is supportive when teachers have health and family issues.

T13: It has a sense of understanding, sees the needs and tries to solve problems, supports the efforts of change and development.

Limited Support

Some responses indicate that support from school management is not always consistent or equal for all teachers. Because of this, some teachers feel excluded, unsupported, or only helped under strict conditions. Their statements are provided in the following excerpts:

T4: I don't feel supported by the school management at all.

T8: Our school management does not support teachers. They support some teachers.

T10: There are rules actually, and everyone acts accordingly, I do not feel or need any extra support from my manager.

T12: I don't think I get enough support from my school management. I feel like my suggestions are not taken into consideration.

Teachers' Views on Teacher Empowerment

Participants were also requested to reflect on teacher empowerment on the survey. They were expected to share their experiences on whether they were allowed to take the responsibility of their teaching, student learning, their professional development and growth by the school management.

Teachers' Views on Teacher Empowerment for Teaching and Learning

Autonomy in Teaching

Some teachers are of the opinion that school management allows them autonomy in their teaching practices and student learning, fostering a sense of responsibility. They feel empowered with freedom in classroom management and teaching methods. Their views are presented as follows:

T2: They do not interfere with our in-class teaching.

T13: They trust teachers and do not interfere with their teaching.

T14: Each teacher is responsible for their own classes and is allowed to guide students according to their needs and wants.

T15: The responsibility is totally yours since no one really interferes with what you do in the class.

Limited Empowerment

Empowerment is sometimes viewed as delegated responsibilities without real decision-making power. Some teachers feel that the empowerment they receive is limited, conditional, or superficial, particularly in terms of autonomy over curriculum or teaching methods. The responses of the participants are like this:

T4: I don't think that they care about it a lot. As teachers, we make decisions about the content of exams and exam dates. I don't think that giving those responsibilities to us was meant as increasing our agency. It was a simple delegation of duties.

T11: Recently, we've started using pop quizzes prepared by our teachers. By doing this, we aimed at giving the teachers the responsibility of their teaching and assessing it.

T5: Not much because the school makes centrally based decisions.

Consequently, autonomy exists at the micro level (lesson delivery), but macro-level decisions (curriculum, structure) are controlled. Teachers report autonomy inside the classroom, but they must follow a centrally designed syllabus. On the other hand, teachers talk about responsibilities like preparing exams or quizzes, but see them as workload delegation rather

than empowerment. Tasks are assigned without genuine trust or professional recognition. In brief, it seems that teachers feel burdened rather than empowered.

Inequities in Empowerment

Participants also perceived disparities in the distribution of empowerment among teachers and departments. Some respondents indicate that certain teachers or units appear to receive greater support or autonomy than others and empowerment is not always equally shared. The excerpts below illustrate these perceptions:

T8: I believe that our school management does not establish equality and they are not interested in creative and talented teachers.

T15: It depends on which part of the university you work at. In faculties, the responsibility is totally yours since no one really interferes with what you do in the class.

In short, teacher empowerment depends on the type of institution or level (faculties vs. primary/high schools). Context matters since different parts of the university or school system grant different levels of autonomy.

Collaboration and Support

Some participants report that school management fosters collaboration by involving teachers in decision-making processes. They think that such practices promote shared responsibility for teaching and student learning. Their reflections are presented below:

T7: They enhance my skills by giving responsibilities because someone has to share all these workloads.

T14: Teachers not only get to cooperate with each other but also make decisions concerning their own classes both through others' feedback and independently.

T9: They encourage people and arrange meetings to talk about education and students.

Teachers highlight positive aspects such as being involved in syllabus/testing, gaining varied experiences, collaborating, and having counsellor support. Responsibilities can enhance skills, encourage cooperation, and foster professional growth. Empowerment is linked to collaboration and professional development opportunities.

Centralized Control

Some teachers feel disempowered by centralised decision-making and a lack of autonomy. Some teachers claim that school management's centralised decision-making limits their ability to take responsibility for their teaching. The following excerpts explain this:

T1: They formulate something in their mind and regard teachers as those who are negligent of their duties or skip them.

T5: The school makes centrally based decisions.

Teachers perceive that management is top-down, distrusting, or uninterested in teacher creativity. Decisions are centralised, teachers are seen as negligent, or equality is not established. Teachers feel disempowered and undervalued.

Responsibility without Support

Teachers feel they have a responsibility but lack sufficient support to fully take ownership of their teaching. Some teachers note that they have responsibility but lack the support or resources to manage it effectively, creating a mismatch between accountability and empowerment.

T15: The responsibility is totally yours since no one really interferes with what you do in the class. The downside of this is that there is no monitoring of what you do there.

T9: They listen to the problems and try to find solutions.

Teachers' Views on Teacher Empowerment for Professional Development

Institutional Support for Professional Development

Some schools provide support for professional development, especially through opportunities for further education. Some respondents report that their school management does provide support, particularly in terms of facilitating access to professional development opportunities like advanced degrees or external events. The excerpts below illustrate these views:

T1: They support it because teachers' individual development and growth also contribute to the development and growth and most importantly to the publicity of the institution.

T9: They support teachers and give responsibility in their professional development.

T14: Our school management encourages each teaching staff member to find, arrange, and follow events and opportunities for professional development and growth.

T13: They inform teachers about some research, seminars, and congresses so that they can join in new areas of research.

Self-Driven Professional Development

Many teachers note that they take responsibility for their own growth, as the institution provides limited guidance or structured opportunities. Some teachers believe that although school management offers a certain level of support, the primary responsibility for professional development is largely left to the teachers themselves. Teachers who seek further growth have to take initiative without significant institutional encouragement or support. They reflect on the issue as follows:

T6: Very few people in my institution try to take the responsibility of their professional development with their own effort rather than their institution.

T7: After graduating, the institutions do not care about the professional development compared to private companies, universities, etc.

T15: You usually don't face any problems when you want to attend an MA, PhD or professional development program.

Lack of Structured Programs

Teachers express dissatisfaction with the lack of organised seminars, workshops, or training opportunities. Many respondents note that the school management lacks structured, consistent programs to actively support professional development, such as workshops, seminars, or in-house training sessions. Some responses are like this:

T4: Some people are doing their degrees and our administrators change schedules according to that. But we never have any seminars or training organized for us.

T8: Nothing is done for professional development.

Support in Higher Education

The data shows that EFL teachers tend to feel more empowered in their professional development due to institutional goals and academic culture. They tend to feel more supported, mainly due to the academic nature of their work and institutional goals that align with continuing education in higher education settings. Some quotations are demonstrated below:

T10: Universities have some academic goals to achieve.

T14: Everybody shares information and experiences with each other on a regular basis, which has been very beneficial regarding both professional development and networking.

Organizational Constraints

Some teachers acknowledge that while school management might not directly hinder their professional development, the overall institutional environment, such as high workload and rigid schedules, presents significant obstacles to teacher empowerment in this area.

T2: Most of the time we have a very busy schedule.

As a result, partial empowerment and freedom occur with such constraints. High workloads and busy schedules prevent many teachers from engaging in professional development, even if they are interested.

Discussion

The findings of the study mainly indicate that participants conceptualise leadership in relational and interpersonal terms, whereas management is mostly associated with administrative and organisational functions. This perception is consistent with contemporary studies emphasising that teacher leadership contributes to collaborative professional cultures and supports school improvement endeavour (Ghamrawi et al., 2024; Wenner & Campbell, 2017) and some other studies which commonly link leadership to creating vision and motivation, while management is related to coordination and the efficient use of resources (Bush, 2011; Northouse, 2019). In the present study, teachers emphasised the roles of guidance, motivation and interpersonal influence when defining leadership, which aligns with transformational leadership perspectives highlighting the role of leaders in inspiring and empowering their subordinates (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2000).

Another important finding is the participants' emphasis on emotional and relational aspects of leadership, which are motivating and supporting colleagues. These perceptions align with previous research suggesting that effective educational leadership involves strong interpersonal relationships and the ability to build trust and collaboration within professional communities (Day & Harris, 2003; Harris, 2008). In particular, the participants' emphasis on cooperation and teamwork reflects the principles of distributed leadership, which conceptualises leadership as a shared practice emerging from interactions among members of an organisation rather than from formal authority alone (Spillane, 2006). Such perspectives are also compatible with teacher leadership frameworks that emphasise teachers' influence beyond the classroom and their contributions to school improvement and professional learning (York-Barr & Duke, 2004). Empirical studies consistently demonstrate that leadership indirectly affects student achievement through mediating variables such as school climate, teacher collaboration, and instructional quality (Cheng, 1994; Sebastian et al., 2016)). Leadership effects are therefore rarely direct; rather, they operate through organisational conditions that shape teaching and learning. This indirect influence strengthens the argument that leadership must be understood as embedded in everyday professional practice rather than isolated within administrative offices.

In contrast, participants tended to define management in more structural and administrative terms. Management was frequently associated with organising resources, controlling processes, solving problems, and ensuring the efficient functioning of the institution. These findings correspond with traditional conceptualisations of management that emphasise planning, coordination, and organisational efficiency (Bush, 2011). The participants' views suggest that teachers perceive management primarily as an institutional responsibility linked to administrative authority rather than as a pedagogical or instructional practice. Only a limited number of participants referred to classroom management or teaching-related aspects when

discussing management. This distinction between leadership and management is consistent with previous studies indicating that educators often perceive leadership as inspirational and people-oriented, whereas management is viewed as procedural and task-oriented (Kotter, 1990; Bush, 2011). However, recent studies suggest that these roles are increasingly interconnected in contemporary educational institutions, particularly in higher education environments where leadership practices often emerge through collaboration among faculty members rather than through hierarchical authority structures (Ghamrawi et al., 2024).

Another noteworthy finding concerns teachers' perceptions of their own leadership roles. Most participants believed that it is essential for teachers to have leadership skills, particularly in relation to motivating students, guiding classroom activities, and supporting student learning. These views correspond with the growing emphasis on teacher leadership in educational research, which highlights teachers' potential to act as facilitators of change, mentors, and contributors to professional learning communities (Katzenmeyer & Moller, 2009; Wenner & Campbell, 2017). Similarly, there are some studies emphasising that teacher leadership can strengthen professional learning communities and improve instructional capacity when teachers are actively involved in organisational processes (Nguyen, Harris, & Ng, 2020; Wenner & Campbell, 2017). However, some participants expressed reservations regarding formal leadership roles, especially administrative positions. Their reluctance was often related to increased workload, limited incentives, or a preference for maintaining professional autonomy. The participants' emphasis on leadership within classroom settings also suggests that teachers often interpret leadership in relation to their instructional responsibilities rather than formal administrative roles. However, limiting teacher leadership to classroom effectiveness may narrow the scope of the concept and overlook its broader organisational implications. Frost and Durrant (2003) caution against restricting teacher leadership to classroom-level practices, emphasising its strategic and developmental contributions across the institution. Similar concerns have been reported in previous studies, which indicate that teachers may hesitate to take on formal leadership responsibilities when such roles are perceived as bureaucratic or disconnected from teaching practices (Mangin & Stoelinga, 2008).

The emerging results also reveal that participants associate effective school leadership with a combination of professional competence, interpersonal skills, organisational ability, and problem-solving capacity. In particular, respondents emphasised the importance of fairness, transparency, communication, and accountability in leadership practices. These expectations correspond with contemporary leadership models that stress ethical leadership, relational trust, and collaborative decision-making within educational organisations (Bryk & Schneider, 2002; Harris, 2008). Teachers' emphasis on transparency and fairness also suggests that trust plays a crucial role in shaping positive perceptions of leadership within educational institutions.

One of the most significant aspects emerging from the findings relates to teachers' perceptions on teacher empowerment. While some participants reported having considerable autonomy in classroom practices, many indicated that decision-making processes related to curriculum design and institutional policies remained centralised. This situation reflects a common tension in educational organisations between professional autonomy and institutional control. Research on teacher empowerment indicates that teachers are more likely to feel professionally motivated and committed when they are actively involved in decision-making processes and when their professional expertise is recognised by institutional leadership (Bogler & Somech, 2004; Lee & Nie, 2021). However, when responsibilities are delegated without genuine participation in decision-making, teachers may perceive such practices as increased workload rather than as meaningful empowerment. In the present study, several participants perceived certain responsibilities, such as preparing exams or quizzes, as

delegated tasks rather than genuine opportunities for professional empowerment. This means that empowerment may sometimes be conceived as an increased workload rather than as enhanced professional agency.

The findings of this study also highlight the role of institutional support in teachers' professional development. Although some participants reported receiving support from school management in the form of flexible schedules, conference participation, or training opportunities, others perceived such support as limited or inconsistent. These mixed perceptions are consistent with previous research suggesting that institutional culture and leadership practices play a crucial role in shaping opportunities for teacher learning and professional growth (Day, 1999; Opfer & Pedder, 2011). In particular, the presence of supportive leadership and collaborative professional cultures has been identified as a key factor in promoting continuous professional development among teachers.

Overall, the results of this study demonstrate that EFL instructors tend to conceptualise leadership as a relational and collaborative process focused on guiding and motivating others, while management is perceived as a more formal and administrative function. Furthermore, teachers recognise the importance of leadership skills in their professional roles. However, their willingness to engage in formal leadership positions may depend on contextual factors such as institutional support, workload, and organisational culture. In a similar vein, Siddiqui et al. (2021) identified several barriers to teacher leadership, such as a lack of time, insufficient administrative support, and organisational structures that limit teacher agency, although teacher leadership development is influenced by teachers' own beliefs, principals' support, and access to professional development opportunities. As suggested by Kasapoğlu and Karaca (2021), to foster teacher leadership in schools, teachers should be given professional development opportunities, particularly through training that focuses on improving leadership skills, since the results of the teachers' perspectives revealed that administration, colleagues, and the hierarchical structure of the system pose significant obstacles for teacher leaders. In line with this, the results of another study yielded a variety of leadership techniques and abilities which would have a positive impact on teachers' well-being such as encouraging cooperation and teamwork, adjusting to changes, respecting teachers' professional judgement, offering emotional support and equitable workload distribution, encouraging work-life balance, offering ongoing feedback and opportunities for professional development, guaranteeing clear communication, empowering and valuing teachers, resolving conflicts, and building trust (Le et al., 2025).

Conclusion

This exploratory study aimed to investigate EFL instructors' perceptions of leadership and management in higher education contexts and to gain a deeper understanding of how these concepts are interpreted based on teachers' professional experiences and institutional environments. The findings of the study provided rich qualitative insights into teachers' definitions of leadership and management, their perceptions of their own leadership roles, their perceptions of teacher empowerment, and the ways in which they develop leadership and management skills within their professional practice. The results indicate that EFL instructors tend to conceptualise leadership primarily as a relational and collaborative process characterised by guidance, motivation, communication, and interpersonal influence. In contrast, management is largely perceived as an administrative and organisational function associated with coordination, control, and resource management within institutional structures. This distinction reflects teachers' tendency to view leadership as a more inspirational and people-oriented process, while management is interpreted as a structural and procedural responsibility. At the same time, the findings suggest that these two concepts are not entirely separate in practice, as leadership and management responsibilities often intersect within educational institutions.

Another important finding concerns teachers' perceptions of their own leadership roles. Although data obtained demonstrated the importance of leadership skills in participants' professional lives, leadership skills are often associated primarily with classroom practices such as guiding students, motivating learners, and facilitating learning processes. The study also put forward important insights regarding teacher empowerment. While many participants reported having a certain level of autonomy in their classroom practices, decision-making processes related to curriculum design, assessment policies, and institutional planning were often perceived as centralised and top-down processes. In this sense, the importance of participatory leadership practices that genuinely involve teachers in institutional decision-making is highlighted. In addition, the findings emphasise the significant role of institutional support in teachers' professional development. Even though some participants reported receiving support from school management in the form of flexible schedules, opportunities to attend conferences, and training programs, others perceived such support as limited or inconsistent. This suggests that leadership practices and institutional culture play a critical role in shaping opportunities for teacher learning, collaboration, and professional growth. Accordingly, such opportunities not only support individual development but also create the structural conditions through which teacher leadership can be enacted and encouraged. It can be concluded that institutional context is a crucial factor in understanding how EFL teachers develop and exercise leadership in higher education.

Furthermore, the results of this study contribute to the growing body of literature on teacher leadership by providing context-specific insights into how EFL instructors perceive leadership and management in higher education environments. The study underlines the importance of fostering collaborative leadership practices, strengthening teacher empowerment, and creating supportive institutional cultures that encourage teachers to take active roles in organisational administrative operations. From a practical perspective, the findings suggest that educational institutions should provide greater opportunities for teachers to participate in decision-making processes and leadership development initiatives. In the context of higher education EFL settings, it may be a good strategy for institutions to implement concrete empowerment strategies such as distributing leadership responsibilities across teaching staff, supporting collaborative professional development, and creating psychologically safe environments where teachers could feel free to voice their perspectives and take initiative so that teacher leadership is not left to chance but becomes a structurally supported institutional priority. Professional development programs focusing on leadership skills and reflective teaching may help teachers expand their leadership capacities beyond classroom settings. In addition, creating transparent and supportive organisational environments may enhance teachers' motivation, professional commitment, and willingness to take responsibilities of leadership roles.

Limitations and Suggestions

This study was conducted with a relatively small group of participants from specific higher education contexts in Türkiye, so the findings should be interpreted within these contextual limitations. Although participants were drawn from multiple institutions, the inclusion of several instructors from the same context may have influenced the representation of the findings. Future research could examine teachers' perceptions of leadership and management across different institutional settings with a larger and equal number of participants, or comparative international contexts. Further studies may also explore how institutional policies, organisational cultures and leadership development programs influence the way teachers perceive teacher leadership practices and professional agency in higher education settings.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank our colleagues and all the other volunteers from different universities who participated in this study. Thanks to their participative approach, we were able to complete the study. It would not have been possible to accomplish this without their help and contributions.

Disclosure of AI Usage

During the preparation of this work, the authors used Copilot and ChatGPT for the purpose of language polishing. Following the use of these tools, the authors reviewed, edited, and validated the content. The final version remains the sole responsibility of the authors.

Ethical Declaration and Committee Approval

This study was conducted in accordance with the principles of scientific research and publication ethics.

Proportion of Authors' Contribution

Author 1: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Data Collection, Formal Analysis, Writing – Original Draft.

Author 2: Conceptualization, Review & Editing, Visualization, Last Draft.

Conflict of Interest

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

References

- Andrianto, S., Komardi, D., & Priyono, P. (2023). Leadership, work motivation, and work discipline on job satisfaction and teacher performance of Dharma Loka Elementary School Pekanbaru. *Journal of Applied Business and Technology*. <https://www.e-jabt.org/index.php/JABT/article/view/117>
- Ash, R. C., & Persall, J. M. (2000). The principal as chief learning officer: Developing teacher leaders. *NASSP Bulletin*, 84(616), 15–22.
- Bailey, K. M. (2006). *Language teacher supervision: A case-based approach*. Cambridge University Press.
- Baker-Doyle, K. J. (2017). *Transformative teacher leadership: A field guide for educators*. Harvard Education Press.
- Bogler, R., & Somech, A. (2004). Influence of teacher empowerment on teachers' organizational commitment, professional commitment, and organizational citizenship behavior in schools. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 20(3), 277–289. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2004.02.003>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Bryk, A. S., & Schneider, B. (2002). *Trust in schools: A core resource for improvement*. Russell Sage Foundation.
- Bryman, A. (2007). Effective leadership in higher education: A literature review. *Studies in Higher Education*, 32(6), 693–710. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075070701685114>
- Bush, T. (2011). *Theories of educational leadership and management* (4th ed.). Sage.
- Cheng, Y. C. (1994). Teacher leadership style: A classroom-level study. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 32(3), 54–71. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09578239410063111>
- Childs-Bowen, D., Moller, G., & Scrivner, J. (2000). Principals: Leaders of leaders. *NASSP Bulletin*, 84, 27–34.
- Cooper, K. S., Stanulis, R. N., Brondyk, S. K., Hamilton, E. R., Macaluso, M., & Meier, J. A. (2016). The teacher leadership process: Attempting change within embedded systems. *Journal of Educational Change*, 17(1), 85–113. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-015-9262-4>
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (3rd ed.). Sage.
- Day, C., & Harris, A. (2003). Teacher leadership, reflective practice and school improvement. In *International handbook of educational administration* (pp. 724–749). Kluwer.
- Deem, R., Hillyard, S., & Reed, M. (2007). *Knowledge, higher education, and the new managerialism: The changing management of UK universities*. Oxford University Press.
- Frost, D., & Durrant, J. (2003). Teacher leadership: Rationale, strategy, and impact. *School Leadership & Management*, 23(2), 173–186.
- Ghamrawi, N., Abu-Shawish, R. K., Shal, T., & Ghamrawi, N. A. R. (2024). Teacher leadership in higher education: Why not? *Cogent Education*, 11(1), Article 2366679. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2024.2366679>
- Gmelch, W. H., & Buller, J. L. (2015). *Building academic leadership capacity: A guide to best practices*. Jossey-Bass.

- Greenleaf, R. K. (1977). *Servant leadership: A journey into the nature of legitimate power and greatness*. Paulist Press.
- Hairon, S., Goh, J. W. P., & Chua, C. S. K. (2015). Teacher leadership enactment in professional learning community contexts: Towards a better understanding of the phenomenon. *School Leadership & Management*, 35(2), 163–182.
- Hallinger, P. (2003). Leading educational change: Reflections on the practice of instructional and transformational leadership. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 33(3), 329–352. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305764032000122005>
- Harris, A. (2003). Teacher leadership as distributed leadership: Heresy, fantasy, or possibility? *School Leadership & Management*, 23(3), 313–324.
- Harris, A. (2008). *Distributed leadership: According to the evidence*. Routledge.
- Hersey, P., Blanchard, K. H., & Johnson, D. E. (2013). *Management of organizational behavior: Leading human resources* (10th ed.). Pearson.
- Hynes, L. J., Pamela, S., & Socoski, P. (1992). Making the lead teacher concept work: The southeast teacher leadership center. *Teaching Education*, 5(1), 43–49.
- Kasapoğlu, H., & Karaca, B. (2021). Teachers' views on teacher leadership: A qualitative analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 17(6), 66–82. <https://doi.org/10.29329/ijpe.2021.382.5>
- Katzenmeyer, M., & Moller, G. (2009). *Awakening the sleeping giant: Helping teachers develop as leaders* (3rd ed.). Corwin.
- Knight, P. T. (2001). Complexity and curriculum: A process approach to curriculum-making. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 6(3), 369–381. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562510120061223>
- Kotter, J. P. (1990). *A force for change: How leadership differs from management*. Free Press.
- Le, T. T., Pham, T. T., & Tran, T. T. (2025). Leadership skills and teacher well-being: Under the lens of Vietnamese EFL teachers. *Educational Point*, 2(1), e114. <https://doi.org/10.71176/edup/16218>
- Lee, M., & Nie, Y. (2021). Understanding teacher empowerment: Teachers' perceptions of principal's and immediate supervisor's empowering behaviours, psychological empowerment, and work-related outcomes. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 106, 103451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2021.103451>
- Leithwood, K., & Jantzi, D. (2000). The effects of transformational leadership on organizational conditions and student engagement with school. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 38(2), 112–129. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09578230010320064>
- Mangin, M. M., & Stoelinga, S. R. (2008). Teacher leadership: What it is and why it matters. In M. M. Mangin & S. R. Stoelinga (Eds.), *Effective teacher leadership: Using research to inform and reform* (pp. 1–9). Teachers College Press.
- Mendez-Morse, S. (1992). Leadership characteristics that facilitate school change. *Issues... About Change*, 1(1), 1–8.
- Nafia, Z. I., & Suyatno, S. (2020). The effect of teachers' leadership on students' motivation in Al-Islam Tambakbayan Elementary School. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(5), 1907–1915. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.080527>
- Netolicky, D. M., Andrews, J., & Paterson, C. (Eds.). (2018). *Flip the system Australia: What matters in education*. Routledge.

- Neumerski, C. M. (2012). Rethinking instructional leadership: A review. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 49, 310–347. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161X12456700>
- Nguyen, D., Harris, A., & Ng, D. (2020). A review of the empirical research on teacher leadership (2003–2017): Evidence, patterns, and implications. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 58(1), 60–80. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEA-02-2019-0027>
- Northouse, P. G. (2019). *Leadership: Theory and practice* (8th ed.). Sage.
- Opfer, V. D., & Pedder, D. (2011). Conceptualizing teacher professional learning. *Review of Educational Research*, 81(3), 376–407. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654311413609>
- Patton, M. Q. (2002). *Qualitative evaluation and research methods* (3rd ed.). Sage.
- Rycroft-Smith, L., & Dutaut, J. L. (2018). *Flip the system UK: A teachers' manifesto*. Routledge.
- Sebastian, J., Allensworth, E., & Huang, H. (2016). The role of teacher leadership in improving instructional practice: The case of distributed leadership. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 52(4), 639–674. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161X15616863>
- Siddiqui, K. A., Chachar, Z. A., Zafar, Z., Dool, M. A., & Kumar, A. (2021). Perceptions of teachers about teacher leadership: A systematic literature review. *MIER Journal of Educational Studies, Trends and Practices*, 11(2), 236–251. <https://doi.org/10.52634/mier/2021/v11/i2/1766>
- Smylie, M. A., Conley, S., & Marks, H. M. (2002). Exploring new approaches to teacher leadership for school improvement. In J. Murphy (Ed.), *The educational leadership challenge: Redefining leadership for the 21st century* (pp. 162–188). National Society for the Study of Education.
- Spillane, J. P. (2006). *Distributed leadership*. Jossey-Bass.
- Spillane, J. P., & Diamond, J. B. (2007). A distributed perspective on and in practice. In J. P. Spillane & J. B. Diamond (Eds.), *Distributed leadership in practice* (pp. 146–166). Teachers College Press.
- Wasley, P. A. (1991). *Teachers who lead: The rhetoric of reform and the realities of practice*. Teachers College Press.
- Wenner, J. A., & Campbell, T. (2017). The theoretical and empirical basis of teacher leadership: A review of the literature. *Review of Educational Research*, 87(1), 134–171.
- York-Barr, J., & Duke, K. (2004). What do we know about teacher leadership? Findings from two decades of scholarship. *Review of Educational Research*, 74(3), 255–316.